

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL DISTANCING ON HEALTH OFFICIAL SERVICES IN PUBLIC MOTHERS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC AT UPT PUSKESMAS SUMBUL DISTRICT, SUMBUL DISTRICT, DAIRI REGENCY IN 2020

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Abstract

The WHO-China Joint Mission on COVID-19 health report estimates a high R₀ (reproduction number) of 2–2.5. The latest report from WHO on March 3, estimated the global death rate which is the infection rate of COVID-19 to be 3.4%. It was first reported in a cohort of 41 patients with laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 pneumonia. The most common symptoms reported were fever (43.8% of cases upon admission and 88.7% during hospitalization) and cough (67.8%). Diarrhea was rare (3.8%). Report of radiological findings on computed tomography (CT) of the chest (56.4%). No radiographic abnormalities were found in 157 of 877 (17.9%) patients with less severe COVID-19 and five of 173 (2.9%) patients with severe symptoms of COVID-19. Lymphocytopenia was reported in 83.2% of patients on admission. This study used a descriptive quantitative research design with a cross sectional approach. The target population in this study were 24 postpartum mothers. The number of samples used was 24 obtained using a total sampling technique. The data analysis technique used the chi square test. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of social distancing on health care worker services in postpartum and breastfeeding during the Covid-19 pandemic at the Sumbul Pegagan District Health Center, Dairi Regency in 2020. The majority of respondents said that social distancing has an effect on the health care services for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic, amounting to 13 people (54.2%) and 11 people (45.8%) said Social Distancing had no effect on health care services for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic. The effectiveness of health care workers with a number of 12 people (50%) said it was not effective and 12 people (50%) said it was effective. There is a social distancing effect on health care services for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic (p value: $0.000 < \alpha: 0.05$). There is a social distancing effect on health care services for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic. It is recommended that health workers improve the best, quality and effective health services to patients, especially midwifery care services for post-partum mothers by following health protocols and optimizing online or telemedicine-based health services.

Keywords: Social Distancing, Health Care Services, COVID-19, Postpartum.

INTRODUCTION

Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) infection, also called SARS-CoV-2, is a global public health emergency. Since the first case of COVID-19 pneumonia was reported in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, in December 2019, the infection has spread rapidly throughout China and areas outside China. Epidemics of two β -coronaviruses, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), have caused more than 10,000 cumulative cases in the last two decades, with a 10% mortality rate for SARS-CoV. and 37% for MERS-CoV. COVID-19 belongs to the same β -coronavirus subgroup and has a genome similarity of about

80% and 50% difference with SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV, respectively. COVID-19 is spread by bootleg droplets and direct contact (when bodily fluids touch another person's eyes, nose or mouth, or open openings of cuts, wounds or abrasions). (*Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol, 2020*).

The World Health Organization (WHO) -China Joint Mission on COVID-19 health report estimates a high R₀ (reproduction number) of 2–2.5. The latest report from WHO on March 3, estimated the global death rate which is the infection rate of COVID-19 to be 3.4%. First reported in a cohort of 41 patients with laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 pneumonia. (WHO, 2020)

The development of the spread of COVID-19 has spread to Indonesia. Positive cases of COVID-19 in Indonesia increased every month by 214 cases in April. That way, the total cases are now 9,096 cases. A total of 1,151 people have been declared cured, 765 people have died, and the rest are still undergoing treatment. Then, the number of people under monitoring (ODP) and patients under surveillance (PDP) is also still increasing. Until now, as much 210,199 people with ODP status and 19,987 people with PDP status. (*Kementeriaan Kesehatan, 2020*)

North Sumatra, with the capital city of Medan, is one of the provinces that has been disabled by the Health Service due to the high rate of spread of COVID-19, Medan City has recorded the highest number of positive cases of COVID-19. The number of positive cases of COVID-19 in Medan City was recorded at 16 people per Monday, an increase from 10 people per Sunday. The latest update was in May 2020, 3,794 ODP cases, 204 PDP cases, 235 positive COVID-19 people, 74 patients recovered, 29 patients died. Meanwhile, other positive cases were spread in Deli Serdang, Langkat and Dairi Regencies. (*Dinkes Prov SUMUT, 2020*)

Maternal and child health is one of the priorities and benchmarks for the development of the health and welfare of a nation, including reducing the maternal mortality rate (MMR) and infant mortality rate (IMR). Based on the results of the 2015 Inter-Census Population Survey (SUPAS) the MMR in Indonesia was 305/100,000 live births. In general, there was a decrease in the maternal mortality rate in the period 1991-2015 from 390/100,000 to 305/100,000 live births. (*SUPAS, 2015*)

The Task Force for the Acceleration of Handling COVID-19 North Sumatra (North Sumatra) displays a map of the distribution of positive cases of COVID-19 in North Sumatra. There are several areas that are included in the red zone, including the Dairi district. The latest data on the spread of COVID-19 in the Dairi district, namely, 3 PDP patients, 2 positive COVID-19 patients, 1 patient recovered. (*Dinkes Prov SUMUT, 2020*)

Dairi Regency is included in the red zone with the number of PDP cases 3 people, 2 people positive, 1 patient recovered, so Social Distancing is strictly implemented to reduce the spread of COVID-19 and Social Distancing has a negative impact on the services of health workers for postpartum mothers at UPT Puskesmas Sumbul Dairy District. Preliminary survey conducted by the author at UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul

District, Dairi Regency in 2020, from the results of an interview with a postpartum mother who was in the UPT Puskesmas Sumbul area, said that Social Distancing greatly affected the service of health workers to postpartum mothers and the results of interviews conducted with mothers Postpartum as many as 5 people related to Social Distancing said that the services provided by health workers during the COVID-19 pandemic were not effective. Based on the background above, the authors are interested in researching "The Influence of Social Distancing on the Services of Health Workers for Postpartum Mothers during the COVID-19 Pandemic Period at UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District, Dairi Regency in 2020"

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative descriptive research design with a cross-sectional approach. The target population in this study were 24 postpartum mothers. The number of samples used was 24 which were obtained using the total sampling technique. The data analysis technique uses the chi square test. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of social distancing on the services of health workers for postpartum and breastfeeding mothers during the Covid-19 pandemic at the Sumbul Pegagan District Health Center, Dairi Regency in 2020.

RESULTS

The distribution of the frequency of health worker services during Social Distancing for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic at the UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District, Dairi Regency in 2020 can be seen in the following table:

Based on table 4.1, it can be concluded that the services of health workers in social distancing for 24 postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic at the UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District, Dairi Regency in 2020, as many as 11 people (45.8%) postpartum mothers said social distancing had no effect on service phealth workers for postpartum mothers and 13 people (54.2%) postpartum mothers said social distancing had an effect on the services of health workers for postpartum mothers.

Table 4.1: Frequency Distribution of health worker services in Social Distancing to Postpartum Mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic at UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District, Dairi Regency in 2020

No.	Social Distancing	Total (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	No	11	45,8%
2.	Yes	13	54,2%
	Total	24	100

Based on table 4.2, it can be concluded that the services of health workers in social distancing for 24 postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic at the UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District, Dairi Regency in 2020, as many as 12 people (50%) postpartum mothers said it was not effective and 12 people (50 %) Postpartum mothers

said that the services of health workers for postpartum mothers were effective during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 4.2: Frequency Distribution of health worker services in Social Distancing to Postpartum Mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic at UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District, Dairi Regency in 2020

No.	Health worker services	Total (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Ineffective	12	50%
2.	Effective	12	50%
	Total	24	100

Based on the table below, it can be concluded that 11 out of 24 postpartum women said Social Distancing had no effect on health worker services, including 1 person (4.17%) said it was not effective and 10 people (41.67%) said health worker services were effective against health worker services. As for 13 postpartum mothers who said that Social Distancing had an effect on health worker services, of them 11 people (45.83%) said it was not effective and 2 people (8.33%) said it was effective for health worker services. The results of the statistical test by conducting the chis quare test obtained the results of p value: $0.000 < \alpha: 0.05$ so that H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted, that is, there was an effect of social distancing on the services of health workers for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic at the UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District Dairi Regency in 2020.

Table 4.3: The effect of Social Distancing on the services of health workers for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic at the UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District, Dairi Regency in 2020

Social Distancing	Health Officer Services				Total		p-value
	Ineffective		Effective				
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Tidak	1	4,17%	10	41,67%	11	45,83%	0,000
Ya	11	45,83%	2	8,33%	13	54,17%	
Total	12	50 %	12	50 %	24	100%	

Analysis of Chi Square Test $p < \alpha = 0,05$

DISCUSSION

Services of health workers in Social Distancing for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic at the UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District, Dairi Regency in 2020

Based on the results of research from 24 respondents to postpartum mothers, 11 people (45.8%) found that social distancing had no effect and 13 people (54.2%) had an effect on the services of health workers for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic. The effectiveness of health worker services with a total of 12 people (50%) said it was ineffective and 12 people (50%) said it was effective. These results were obtained through

questionnaire questions where most said social distancing had an effect on health worker services. Worried about the spread of COVID-19, because the spread of the virus occurs when people interact socially and have physical contact. To prevent this, social interaction is limited, such as studying at home, working from home, and praying at home, which is known as social distancing. Even if they meet physically, it must be done within a distance of no less than two meters or while adhering to the health protocol. (Wilder-Smith, A., & Freedman, 2020)

The application of social distancing is carried out based on guidelines set by the government, the community has an important role in breaking the chain of transmission of COVID-19 so as not to create new sources of transmission. Given the method of transmission based on droplet infection from individual to individual, transmission can occur both at home, travel, workplaces, places of worship, tourist attractions and other places where there are people who interact socially. In principle, prevention and control of COVID-19 in the community is carried out by preventing transmission. In individuals such as cleaning hands regularly by washing hands with soap and running water for 40-60 seconds or using an alcohol-based hand sanitizer (handsanitizer) for at least 20-30 seconds, avoiding touching eyes, nose and mouth with unclean hands, and protecting public health such as prevention efforts (prevent), case finding (detct), penanganan secara cfast and effective (responsive). (KMK RI no 413, 2020)

The services of health workers for postpartum mothers during social distancing have changed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, because medical staff also feel worried and aware of the spread of the virus, although they continue to provide midwifery care services by implementing health protocols that have been set by the government with the principles of preventing COVID-19 19 principles for postpartum women in the community include universal precautions by always washing hands with soap for 20 seconds or hand sanitizer, using personal protective equipment, maintaining body condition by exercising diligently and getting enough rest, eating a balanced diet, and practicing cough-sneeze etiquette . (Kemenkes RI, 2020)

The effect of Social Distancing on the services of health workers for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic at the UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District, Dairi Regency in 2020

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that 11 out of 24 postpartum women said Social Distancing had no effect on health worker services, including 1 person (4.17%) said it was ineffective and 10 people (41.67%) said health worker services were effective against health worker services. As for the 13 postpartum mothers who said that Social Distancing had an effect on health worker services, of them 11 people (45.83%) said it was ineffective and 2 people (8.33%) said it was effective for health worker services. The results of the statistical test by carrying out the chis quare test obtained the results of p value: $0.000 < \alpha: 0.05$ so that H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted, that is, there was an effect of social distancing on the services of health workers in postpartum mothers

during the COVID-19 pandemic at the UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District Dairi Regency in 2020.

This research is in accordance with research conducted by Julia A Bielicki (2020) in her article saying that health workers are very important for any health care system. During the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, healthcare workers substantially increased their risk of being infected with the virus, severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS-CoV-2) and the consequences of which could pose considerable harm. Depending on the phase of the pandemic, patients with COVID-19 may not be the main source of infection with SARS-CoV-2 and healthcare workers may be exposed to atypical patients, infected family members, direct contacts, or living in a community of transmission. aktif. Strategi yang jelas untuk mendukung dan dengan tepat mengelola petugas infected persons is essential to ensure effective management of staff and to engender trust in the workplace. Policy makers need to support health care facilities in interpreting guidelines during a pandemic which may be characterized by fluctuating local occurrences of SARS-CoV-2 to reduce the impact of this pandemic on their workforce.

The service of health workers is the ability of an organization to provide and meet customer expectations indicating the quality of service of an organization, so the customer's assessment of the service that has been received by the customer will give an idea of the quality of service. Quality must start from customer needs and end with achieving good service quality. Meanwhile, during the current pandemic, based on research by Sanwang Wang et al, it was said that due to the COVID-19 pandemic, increased stress could be experienced by medical personnel which could affect the performance of health workers' services to patients, such as the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of health services.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion regarding the effect of social distancing on the services of health workers for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic at the UPT Puskesmas Sumbul, Sumbul District, Dairi Regency in 2020, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The majority of respondents said Social Distancing had an effect on the services of health workers for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic, totaling 13 people (54.2%) and 11 people (45.8%) said Social Distancing had no effect on services for health workers on mothers postpartum during the COVID-19 pandemic. The effectiveness of health worker services with a total of 12 people (50%) said it was ineffective and 12 people (50%) said it was effective.
2. There is an effect of Social Distancing on the services of health workers for postpartum mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic (p value: $0.000 < \alpha: 0.05$)

SUGGESTION

1. Educational institutions are expected to be able to improve the quality of education for students by providing facilities and infrastructure during the COVID-19 pandemic to support increasing student competence so that they can produce quality medical personnel.
2. It is hoped that health workers will further improve the best, quality and effective health services for patients, especially midwifery care services for postpartum mothers by following health protocols and optimizing online or telemedicine-based health services.
3. It is hoped that the community, especially postpartum mothers, will take better care of the health of their mothers and babies during a pandemic and continue to implement health protocols.
4. For future researchers to examine the effect of health services on improving the quality of health services in the new normal era.

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